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BOOK REVIEW

BENEFIT SEGMENTING SMALL PASSENGER CAR MARKET: A MICRO ANALYSIS OF NCR

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Abstract

Market segmentation is becoming more and more complex with increase in number of parameters being used in the process. Only priori segmentation has no longer of any use. The benefit sought from the product is increasingly being used. It requires knowledge and uses of multivariate analytical tools. Cluster analysis is extensively being used for segmenting the market. This article presents a case of benefit segmenting small passenger car market. The main problem examine in this research is what are the perceived benefits customers look for in a passenger car? Can we use those benefits to segment the market? The model followed in this research is a hybrid model which is a mix of both priori segmentation and benefit segmentation. Hierarchical Agglomerate clustering with average linkage is used along with k-means clustering through SPSS 16 Processor. The research is conducted in the NCR region and is confined to small cars only.

Introduction

Though Industrial sector has witnessed a slow down in the fiscal year 2007-2008 but the production of automotive industry grew at an impressive rate during the Tenth Five Year Plan. Particularly the production of passenger cars grew by 15.6 per cent. Today, the Indian auto industry is one of the largest industrial sectors with a turnover that contributes to roughly 5 per cent of India's GDP.

As a result of Liberalization, the capacity of car production has increased substantially and is expected to grow manifold in the coming years. The industry is subject to tremendous changes particularly in the segment of small passenger cars. With Tata announcing the launch of "Nano", (a very price competitive passenger car) and with a few more players expected to follow the suit, the competition seems to be more intensified in small segment passenger car sector, in times to come. To meet the challenges, manufacturers will have to strive to cut costs, enhance market orientation, improve performance, and successfully create a high level of customer loyalty.

The Passenger Cars can be classified in to; Small Segment cars, Mid Segment Cars, Premium Cars and Luxury Cars. Under the new norms formulated by SIAM (society of Indian Automobile manufacturers) some times in the first half of 2002, along the International lines, passenger cars in India will now be classified (according to 'Bumper to Bumper' lengths) under six categories: Mini: up to 3,400mm; Compact:

3,401-4,000mm; Mid-size: 4,001-4,500mm; Executive: 4,501-4,700 mm; Premium: 4,701-5,000mm; & Luxury: 5,001mm & above.

Literature Review: The need to understand the consumer behavior in Passenger cars, is important to the decision makers, be they the marketers or intellectuals interested in scientific research. The rapid development of the Indian Auto industry, especially after the 1991 economic measures, forced the marketers to conduct more research studies on consumer behavior.

Rengandathan (2005) conducted a study on consumer markets and buying behavior of cars and found the most of the Indian respondents are focused towards mileage in a car. Chidambaram et al (2004) conducted a study on brand preference of passenger cars at Coimbatore city of Tamil Nadu. He too concluded that most respondents give more advantage to fuel efficiency. So far as consumer purchase decision making is concerned, the passenger car being high value product requires a high effort judgment and decision making. Scott Smith (1997) has shown factors like convenience, status and pressure from known source is paramount.

Individual factors affecting the purchase decision is just not sufficient to device a strategy. Purchases involve consideration of both product performance and psychosocial consequences, those relating to purchaser's self concept and the reactions of other people. In case of passenger car product performance with demographic profile can be used to create a hybrid segment. Therefore group of customers sharing similar likings need to be identified. Benefit segmenting is the way to obtain the market segment on the basis of the benefit customer's seeks from the product.

Marketer provided information often does not provide the possible negative consequences

of the purchase. To evaluate these psychosocial consequences, the potential buyer may ask his friends or coworkers for advice (William and Leahman), 1990. The study of the customer mind set, influencing forces, segments will help the marketers of the passenger cars in targeting the audience, positioning their products and designing suitable promotional strategies.

Market segmentation: A market segment consists of a group of customers who share a similar set of needs and wants. The marketers' does not create a segment but their job is to identify the segments and decide which one to target (Kotler).

Market segments can be defined in many ways. One way is to identify the market segments through customer preferences. For example, a passenger car is identified by a group of customers on variables, such as fuel economy and safety; the results could be any of the three cases.

Homogeneous preference: It shows a market where all the consumers have roughly the same set of preference.

Diffused segments: Consumer preference may be scattered throughout the space, indicating that consumers vary greatly in their preferences.

Clustered preference: The market might reveal distinct preference clusters, called natural market segments.

Through in general the above two cases are rarely observed in the era of customer oriented markets, where customers are very particular about their requirements.

Segmenting Consumer Markets: Two broad variables are used to segment consumers markets. It is not like only one of them can be used but for better results both are used simultaneously. These variables represent the following two broad market characteristics; Descriptive

Characteristics: Like geographic, demographic, and psychographic etc., and Behavioral Characteristics: Such as benefit sought from product, use occasions or brands.

Initially we start with one of them, which we think has a broad distinction of the customers on one of its type. Once the segments are formed, the researcher sees whether different characteristics are associated with each consumer response segment. For e.g. we might examine whether people who want quality rather than low price in buying an automobile differ in their geographic, demographic, and psychographic makeup.

In this study Behavioral characteristic viz. benefit sought from the product is considered as main bases for segmentation. Initially the price band of the car was used to identify the sector to conduct the study. As a result this study is confined to small cars only. After doing the behavioral segmentation, the demographics of the market was studied to get a better insight of the market.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the research are:

- To segment the small passenger car market on the basis of benefit sought.
- To prepare demographic profile of the small passenger car consumers, such as income, age, gender etc.
- To identify the main reasons that affects a car purchase decision.

Research Methodology

A descriptive research design involving a sample size of 152 respondents was used for this purpose. On the basis of Literature review and informal discussions with a group of regular car

drivers and industry experts around 39 possible reasons were identified which may be considered by the customers in a passenger car buying decision. The variables selected are finally based on prior Principle component analysis conducted before this study. The following variables are included; Safety, Status, Operating Expense, Comfort, Features, Price, and Power.

For the matter of data collection a structured questionnaire was used as research instrument. A 5 point Likert scale was used for the purpose of data collection. Most of the collected data was interval data besides a few which was nominal, describing the demographic profiles of customers. Further the interval data collected is standardized using the z scale. The data after rescaling each variable have a mean of zero and a standard deviation of unity.

The field work was done during the early months of year 2009. Sampling technique adopted was non probability quota sampling. With in a quota the method of convenience sampling was adopted. The study was conducted in the NCR region. Since a considerable large portion of the population of small car (by small in this research we mean mini, compact and mid size car as per SIAM classification) segment reside in this region, it is reasonably good to conduct the study here. All the data collection was done in the NCR region. Most of the respondents were contacted at various Service Stations or Garage in the region. A few were contacted in different shopping malls across the region. The idea was to cover respondents of all income and age groups. A total of 240 respondents were contacted for this purpose; out of which 56 did not respond. 32 of the questionnaire were incomplete or casually filled hence not included in the analysis.

Conducting Cluster Analysis

The technique allows partitioning an original population into subsets called clusters, so that data in each subset share some common trait-proximity according to some defined distance measure. The goal is to bring together individuals having relatively similar characteristics while individuals from different groups are as distant as possible. The present study is conducted using Agglomerative Hierarchical Clustering with average linkage. The main steps of the cluster formation are as follows. Let there be n observations with m characteristics. At the beginning all observations are considered as separate groups. A similarity index, the Euclidean distance between the average scores of two clusters is computed for all $n(n-1)/2$ potential pairs of observations and the two nearest are grouped into one cluster. In the next step the same procedure is repeated for remaining $n-1$ pairs and $(n-1)(n-2)/2$ distances are compared for grouping. The process goes on since all the observations are grouped as one single cluster, hence creating a hierarchy.

The method leaves a choice to decide the number of clusters. Various methods are defined for this purpose. In this study the collected interval data were subject to Agglomerative Hierarchical Clustering with average linkage, using SPSS 16 processor.

Hence the coefficients (distance) given in the agglomerate schedule is used to decide the number of clusters. The moment a steep rise is noticed in the cluster distance, further clustering is stopped.

Demographic profile of respondents: As evident from the sample about 78% respondents were males. Marital status shows around 9% were unmarried and 2% divorce. Income distribution shows about 30% were having an income of above 50k. Around 60% of the respondents have the family as the owner while rests were individual owners. Only 6% were retired and 10% were students and 20% were self employed. 22% were in the age group of 18-30, 65% were in the age group of 30-55. A detailed summary is given in Table 1.

Table 1

Gender	Male	Female	
	78%	22%	
Marital Status	Married	Unmarried	Divorce
	89%	9%	2%
Monthly Income	? 50K	? 50K	Non Earners
	30%	54%	16%
Family Status	Family Men	Individuals	
	60%	40%	
Employment Status	Employed	Retired	Students
	84%	6%	10%
Age Group	18-30	30-55	? 55
	22%	65%	11%

Interpretation: It is evident from the study that in the small car sector price band is the first basis to entry. Once the price band is selected then the question of further narrowing down begins. Here the population shows a significant amount of

heterogeneity, which has been identified. The following groups/clusters have been identified with a few exceptions which were not included in anywhere.

Table 2

Agglomeration Schedule						
Stage	Cluster		Coefficients	Stage Cluster First		Next Stage
	Combined			Appears		
	Cluster 1	Cluster 2		Cluster 1	Cluster 2	
1	149	152	0.00	0	0	4
2	121	151	0.00	0	0	32
146	31	32	8.89	141	131	148
147	22	23	9.00	144	80	149
148	31	35	12.17	146	138	150
149	1	22	46.25	139	147	150
150	1	31	48.62	149	148	151
151	1	39	114.14	150	145	0

The distance between fourth and fifth rows in the coefficient columns in the agglomerate schedule (Table-2) is the highest (46.248-12.167). It suggests that a four cluster solution is ideal. Further the k-means cluster procedure was adopted pre specifying the means as four. The

Final cluster centers (Table-3) were obtained which described the mean value of each variable for all the four clusters. Number of cases as given in Table-4 describes the distribution of respondents in the clusters formed.

Table 3

Final Cluster Centers				
	Cluster			
	1	2	3	4
Safety	6.44	6.73	6.63	6.67
Operating Expenses	6.22	2.00	5.13	6.81
Status	1.67	6.41	1.38	1.33
Power	1.67	6.00	6.25	1.47
Price	6.00	2.24	6.38	6.67
Comfort	6.33	6.24	1.38	1.58
Features	5.78	6.57	5.38	1.52

Cluster Interpretation

Cluster 1: The first cluster comprises of those respondents who are more concerned about the money part of the car purchase. Psycho stimulants hardly play any role in their purchase decision. The maximum weight age is given to the price and operating expenses. The demographics shows, that the ownership pattern in most of the cases is family. Maximum are either of young age or middle aged people. Source of earning is job and most of them have a monthly income of less than 50K in a month. They are not risk takers hence can not experiment and therefore believe in generic brands. Word of mouth is the main deciding factor in their purchase decision. They generally purchase a car with an intention of long term holding usually up to 10-15 years.

Cluster 2: This cluster shows little less concern towards the monetary part of car purchase. But it shows a considerable interest towards features and comfort in a passenger car. Demographics shows most of them are either females or old aged people. Both types of ownership, individual and family are observed in the cluster. Monthly income is moderate and in age the cluster is quite homogeneous. They also don't want to change their vehicle quite often. The purchase is done to keep the vehicle for most of the part of its useful life.

Cluster 3: This cluster also consider prices as one of the distinguishing factor. Besides features, power also is seen as a dominating factor. Demographics reveal that the cluster mainly comprises of young individuals. The occupation is either student or young members of business families. Ownership is mainly individual. They are risk takers and try to experiment with new

offerings. They don't have an intention to keep a vehicle for a long time.

Cluster 4: Finally there is a cluster of respondents which is not so particular on pricing aspect of a passenger car. More focus is given on status and comfort ability. Demographics show that ownership is mostly individual. Most of them are mid aged executives having a monthly income of more than 50K. They generally prefer to keep a vehicle for a period of around 5-7 years.

Table 4

Number of Cases in each Cluster		
Cluster	1	27
	2	37
	3	24
	4	64
	Valid	152
	Missing	

Conclusion

As revealed by the study a four cluster solution exists in the chosen sector. Further demographics variables have shown better insights as to how the benefit sought from the product is related to the demographic characteristics of the respondents. It will help the marketers to design their communication and product strategies accordingly. It also provides a scope for further narrowing down to find out a niche in a segment by conducting further analysis.

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